

D5.1 – Database of funding opportunities

Date: 24/05/2023

Doc. Version: Version 1

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

**GEMSTONE (101078981)-Genetically Engineering Experimental Models:
Enhancement of Scientific and Technological Excellence an Innovation Potential to
Study Neurodevelopmental Diseases**

Action Number: [HORIZON Coordination and Support
Action]

Action Acronym: [HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-
03]

Action title: [GEMSTONE- Genetically Engineering
Experimental Models: Enhancement of Scientific and
Technological excellence and innOvation potential to study
NEurodevelopmental diseases]

Date: [24.05.2023]

Version: [Version 1]

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Changes
1.0	24.05.2023	Initial version

Settings	Value
Document Title:	D5.1 – Database of funding opportunities
Deliverable number	5.1
Project Title:	Genetically Engineering Experimental Models: Enhancement of Scientific and Technological Excellence an Innovation Potential to Study Neurodevelopmental Diseases
Document Author:	Serena Cogoni (ICONS), Sinem Bagece (ACU)
Project Owner	Prof. Dr. Filiz Onat, ACU (Coordinator), Deniz Kirik, ULUND, Serena Cogoni, ICONS
Doc. Version:	Version 1
Sensitivity:	Public
Date:	24/05/2023

Document Control Information

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

Name	Role	Action	Date
Serena Cogoni	Local PI of GEMSTONE, ICONS	<i>Creation and the first draft of the document</i>	24/05/2023

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

Table of Content

Introduction 5
Scope of this document 6
Methodology 6
Database of funding opportunities..... 8

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

Introduction

Acibadem Mehmet Ali Aydınlar University (ACU), based in Istanbul, is the biggest thematic university in the field of health in Turkey. Its mission is to be an academic institution which creates a model for Turkey, and which is shown as a reference in the world, with its high level of excellence, culturally and socially well equipped, dedicated to creating individuals who value ethical principles, who ensure modern, innovative and pioneering practices.

Although ACU's brand is appreciated in the Balkan countries and Turkey, lot of activities still need to be performed, to give ACU the opportunity to compete with leading European universities.

The GEMSTONE project aims to increase the ACU research excellence by improving the research staff expertise, expanding the network of scientific collaborations and building the overall capacity of the organization, so that it can become a leader in the health field.

A survey taken during the preparation of the GEMSTONE application collected some indicators to evaluate the reputation, research profile and attractiveness of the universities involved in the project and revealed a disparity in terms of number of publications in prestigious journals, top cited researchers, top cited papers and number of external networks linking to the institution's webpage.

One of the aims of the GEMSTONE project is to create the ideal conditions, knowledge and skills to allow researchers to submit papers in high impact journals, participate and lead international research project and attract funding, be more visible within the European and global neuroscience community and increase their networking capacities and opportunities.

We included a specific work package (WP5), providing researchers with the necessary knowledge and skills to submit successful grant applications, attract funds, translate research results to clinics and/or in commercial products, thus ensuring that ACU will become the ideal place to express ACU researchers' potential.

One of the Task of this Work package (Task 5.2) is entirely dedicated to the identification and analysis of funding opportunities available for the GEMSTONE researchers. The first step is constituted by the search for the existing and upcoming grants and funding opportunities that are related to the research performed within GEMSTONE at national, European and global level (e.g. European Commission, charities, foundations, etc).

For each opportunity, partners are analysing expected aims, eligible activities, and general eligibility criteria (in terms of country, type of organization, legal form...), to define which opportunities may be suitable for the participation of the involved organisations, both as Coordinator/main applicant, or partner.

A database was planned to be created by month 8 and maintained along the project duration, in line with the publication of new funding opportunities.

Funding opportunities will be prioritized according to specific parameters (such as deadline, complexity of the application, level of funding, number and extent of collaborations required...) and a Gantt chart will be created to provide an overall picture of all concrete possibilities up to the end of the project.

A strategic workshop will be organised among project partners at month 9 to discuss suitable grant opportunities.

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

As an indicator to the success of this Work package, we planned that at least 3 grants application would be submitted during the project duration, of which one may be an EU proposal (e.g. Horizon Europe), one a philanthropic funding source application (e.g., Michael J. Fox Foundation for Parkinson's disease), and at least one national application (e.g., to the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TUBITAK)).

Scope of this document

This document includes a list of funding opportunities in the field of neuroscience and basic research, that are close to the area in which GEMSTONE is operating and that may be considered to support complementary research lines, among the consortium partners.

As mentioned in the Introduction, the database will be complemented with further details on the calls for proposals and funding opportunities will be analysed, prioritized and then discussed during a strategic workshop that is currently under organisation.

Given its public nature, this document is also designed to help researchers and organizations in neuroscience and basic research outside GEMSTONE find funding opportunities that match their interests and needs. For each of the opportunities identified, we included a link, where researchers and organisations can find more details to evaluate their eligibility and fitting with the scope of the call announcement.

Methodology

We created the list of available funding opportunities by searching the web for relevant opportunities in the field of neuroscience or in basic research in general.

The database is divided into three sections:

- national funding opportunities,
- European funding opportunities, and
- global funding opportunities.

For each section, the following information are provided:

- The programme name or the call title
- The deadline within which an application must be submitted
- Tags identifying the nature and scope of the call (selected among #research, #training, #mobility, #networking)
- The link to the call announcement

While preparing the list of national funds, we evaluated TÜBİTAK's basic scientific research programs, and bilateral and multi-collaboration programs (International Support Programmes of TUBITAK) for our

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

researchers. We have included urgent support funds for career development for young researchers and PhD Candidates. The researchers with a doctorate or bachelor's degree who conduct research with a full-time contract in the Republic of Turkey or the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus can benefit from TÜBİTAK funds. On the other hand, the researchers working in foreign countries can participate in the project teams if they create a researcher profile on the TUBİTAK website (<https://arbis.tubitak.gov.tr/home.jsf>) even if they are not the principal investigator. All the detailed information about TUBİTAK's funding opportunities can be reached on the webpage: <https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/en/funds/academy/national-support-programmes>

The most common funding institution in the field of health, other than TÜBİTAK supports, is TUSEB, which is affiliated with the Ministry of Health. Two research and development support funds of TUSEB, suitable for experienced and young researchers, have been added to this deliverable. Neuroscience is among the priority fields for TUSEB. TUSEB's calls are only available in Turkish. The updated calls are available on the webpage: <https://proje-destek.tuseb.gov.tr/>

At European level, we evaluated the opportunities offered by the Horizon Europe programme by searching through the Funding and Tenders Opportunities Portal and by reading the relevant Work programmes 2023-2024. As the Horizon Europe calls are not prescriptive, we searched for those opportunities supporting basic research, training and career growth opportunities and networking.

Other opportunities offered by European associations have been included as well.

As for the global opportunities, we looked for non-profit associations that are currently funding research in neuroscience and, in particular, in epilepsy and Parkinson's disease. As most of them are based outside Europe, we also verified that European countries were also eligible to apply.

This database will be revised periodically and further strategic workshops will be organised along the project duration, to intercept future funding opportunities.

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

Database of funding opportunities

Opportunities at national level (Turkey)

Programme name / call title	Deadline	Tag	Link to the announcement
TÜBİTAK ARDEB 1001- The Scientific and Technological Research Projects Funding Program	Each year March and September (The deadlines are announced in TUBITAK website)	#research	https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/en/funds/academy/national-support-programmes/content-1001-the-scientific-and-technological-research-projects-funding-program
TÜBİTAK ARDEB 1002 Short Term R&D Funding Program	Applications accepted throughout the year.	#research	https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/en/funds/academy/national-support-programmes/content-1002-short-term-rd-funding-program
TÜBİTAK ARDEB 3501 Career Development Program (CAREER)	Applications accepted throughout the year	#research	https://www.tubitak.gov.tr/en/funds/academy/national-support-programmes/content-3501-career-development-program-career
TÜBİTAK 1071	To be announced	#research	https://uidb-pbs.tubitak.gov.tr/
Bilateral Cooperation Programs – Funded by TÜBİTAK	Either rolling base or call based, depending on the countries	#research #mobility	Programs_Open to Continuous Application: 2501 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with the US National Science Foundation (NSF) 2502 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS) 2507 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with the German Research Council (DFG) 2526 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with Mongolian Academy of Sciences (MAS) 2591- Belarus Industry Academy Cooperation Program with Innovation Agency (BIF) On-Call Support Programs: 2509 - Bosphorus Program with the French Ministry of Foreign Affairs

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

			2523 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with Korea National Research Foundation (NRF) 2530 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with Moldovan Research and Development Agency (NARD) 2537 - Czech Republic Academy of Sciences (Bilateral Cooperation Program with CAS) 2540 - Thematic Cooperation Program with the Slovak Academy of Sciences (SAS) 2556 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with Qatar National Research Fund (QNRF) 2565 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with Malta Science and Technology Council (MCST) 2568 - Bilateral Cooperation Program with Chinese Academy of Sciences (CAS)
2515 COST Support Program European Cooperation Organization in Science and Technology	Applications accepted throughout the year	#research	http://uidb-pbs.tubitak.gov.tr/
2519 - COST Working Group Support Program Organization for European Cooperation in Science and Technology	Applications accepted throughout the year	#research	http://uidb-pbs.tubitak.gov.tr/
Health Institutes of Turkey- TUSEB	4th Term A4-04: 01.10.2023-31.12.2023	#research	https://tbys.tuseb.gov.tr/#/aktifcagrilistesidispanel
TUSEB for PhD Candidates	2nd Term: 01.09.2023-31.10.2023	#research	https://tbys.tuseb.gov.tr/#/aktifcagrilistesidispanel

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

Opportunities at European level

Programme name / call title	Deadline	Tag	Link to the announcement
MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2023 & 2024	13/09/2023 (for 2023) and 11/09/2024 (for 2024)	#training #mobility	Funding & tenders (europa.eu) (call 2023) Funding & tenders (europa.eu) (call 2024)
MSCA Staff Exchanges 2023 & 2024	24/02/2024 (for 2023) and 05/03/2025 (for 2024)	#training #mobility #networking	Funding & tenders (europa.eu) (call 2023) Funding & tenders (europa.eu) (call 2024)
MSCA Doctoral Networks 2023 & 2024	28/11/2023 (for 2023) and 27/11/2024 (for 2024)	#training #mobility #networking	Funding & tenders (europa.eu) (call 2023) Funding & tenders (europa.eu) (call 2024)
HORIZON-HLTH-2024-DISEASE-03-13-two-stage: Validation of fluid-derived biomarkers for the prediction and prevention of brain disorders	19/09/2023 (first stage) – 11/04/2024 (second stage)	#research	Funding & tenders (europa.eu)
HORIZON-HLTH-2024-TOOL-05-06-two-stage: Innovative non-animal human-based tools and strategies for biomedical research	19/09/2023 (first stage) – 11/04/2024 (second stage)	#research	Funding & tenders (europa.eu)
HORIZON-HLTH-2024-DISEASE-03-14-two-stage: Tackling high-burden for patients, under-researched medical conditions	19/09/2023 (first stage) – 11/04/2024 (second stage)	#research	Funding & tenders (europa.eu)
EAN Research Fellowship	31/08/2023	#training #mobility	Research Fellowship - ean.org
EMBO Scientific Exchange Grants	Applications accepted throughout the year	#mobility #networking	Fellowships, grants and career support – Scientific Exchange Grants – EMBO
EMBO Advanced Collaboration Grants	Applications accepted throughout the year	#mobility #networking	Fellowships, grants and career support – Advanced Collaboration Grants – EMBO

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.

Opportunities at global level

Programme name / call title	Deadline	Tag	Link to the announcement
CURE Epilepsy Award	To be announced (deadline usually in early January each year)	#research	CURE Epilepsy Grant Program and Grant Opportunities
Taking Flight Award	To be announced (last deadline in January 2023)	#research	CURE Epilepsy Grant Program and Grant Opportunities
Rare Epilepsy Partnership Award	June 26, 2023	#research	CURE Epilepsy Grant Program and Grant Opportunities
The Boehringer Ingelheim Fonds – PhD fellowships	February 1, June 1, and October 1 of each year	#research #mobility	PhD fellowships (bifonds.de)
The Boehringer Ingelheim Fonds – Travel grants	No earlier than six months prior to the planned date of departure.	#training #research #mobility	Travel grants (bifonds.de)
The Human Frontier Science Program (HFSP) – Research grants	To be announced (last deadline: March 2023)	#research	Research Grants Human Frontier Science Program (hfsp.org)
The Michael J. Fox Foundation - Parkinson's Disease Therapeutics Pipeline Program	July 27, 2023	#research	Parkinson's Disease Therapeutics Pipeline Program Parkinson's Disease (michaeljfox.org)
CURE Parkinson's – Quarterly Research Grant Funding Programme	4 times a year (the last one for 2023 is October 16, 2023)	#research	https://cureparkinsons.org.uk/for-researchers/apply-for-funding/quarterly-research-grant-funding/

The GEMSTONE Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement number 1010789881.